

Conference Abstract

Diversity of hemipenes and its taxonomical implication in the genus *Ablepharus* (Squamata: Scincidae)

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Abstract

The genus *Ablepharus* encompasses 10 species and 12 subspecies, distributed from Hungary to India. Most species and subspecies have been described from the Middle East and Central Asia, based on external morphology (pholidosis, body size and coloration). The present study is an attempt to demonstrate the hemipenial morphology throughout the genus. Some taxonomical questions arose during comparison of the hemipenes of several subspecies and species, showing the necessity of a revision of the genus. A dendrogram generated from distinctive hemipenial characters revealed rapid divergence of this structure in closely related taxa and discrepancy with the phylogenetic tree based on molecular data from previous studies.

Keywords

skink, morphology, hemipenis, relationships

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